

IMPROVEMENT OF INFORMATION CULTURE IN FUTURE TEACHERS

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Annotation. This article analyzes the essence of information culture and examines the problems of its formation. It also highlights new opportunities created by modern information and communication technologies in addressing these problems. The article investigates the new requirements for information culture in the context of an information society and outlines ways to develop it.

Keywords: information culture, information society, information environment, information and communication technology

At the global level, the intensification of informatization in many countries, alongside deepening democratic reforms and increasing social activity of every citizen, creates conditions for developing theoretical perspectives on these processes and practical experiences in this sphere.

The experience of developed countries demonstrates that fostering independence, self-development, and the constant generation of new ideas during the preparation of future professionals for their careers in higher educational institutions, along with conducting classes on didactic foundations, demands the informatization of educational processes and the cultivation of an information culture in every student. This is linked to the fact that information culture enables individuals to select data from the vast world of information that serves societal development.

In developed countries, the rapid advancement of information systems and telecommunications technologies positively influences the quality and effectiveness of education, expanding opportunities through the use of digital educational resources and interactive software tools. The introduction of innovative ideas in education has become a driving force behind achieving high results in the educational field.

In the context of adapting global education systems to sustainable development trends, the priority tasks include refining interactive educational strategies and mechanisms based on modern development principles. This involves preparing creative specialists who can plan their activities and think divergently. These objectives emphasize the importance of psychological and pedagogical approaches to the effective use of electronic educational resources,

the high-quality implementation of interactive educational services, and the integration of the educational process and environment with active information exchange.

In Uzbekistan, as part of the reforms aimed at fundamentally renewing the teacher training system, developing electronic educational and methodological resources, improving the mechanisms for effectively utilizing interactive software tools with innovative approaches, and strengthening the material and technical base, the level of integration of modern information technologies and software tools into the educational process has significantly increased [1].

Information culture, alongside the development of capabilities such as human innovation in science, technology, production, culture, and other spheres, as well as preparing individuals for professional activities in new living conditions, fosters the ability to act independently and addresses issues of protection against negative influences. Mastery of information contributes to developing critical thinking, worldviews, knowledge, experience, and talents. Through the study of information, individuals engage in searching, observing, researching, analyzing results, and drawing conclusions.

In this regard, significant attention is given to the formation of information culture among youth, particularly university students, in scientific centers, training courses, and projects in developed countries. Information culture occupies a vital place in education, scientific knowledge, independent learning, leisure, and other areas of personal activity.

Definitions of Information Culture in Literature: According to N.B. Zinovieva, "Information culture is the comprehensive development of an individual's inner world through the assimilation of socially significant material" [2]

A.A. Grechikhin, while asserting that the formation of information culture occurs through informational activity, defines it as follows: "Information culture is informational activity of an axiological nature, i.e., interconnected cultural values" [3].

I.G. Khangeldiev describes it as "a qualitative characteristic embodying universal spiritual values that an individual acquires through the assimilation, transmission, storage, and use of information in their life and activities".

E.L. Semenyok perceives information culture as a characteristic of a person. According to her, the formation of information culture reflects the development of humanitarian ideas and personal relationships on the basis of knowledge.

Thus, the extensive use of information in educational activities shapes knowledge, skills, and abilities relevant to professional activities. During the learning process, special attention is given to explaining the use and analysis of information, data collection, systematization, and computer processing, studying periodicals, enhancing educational and instructional processes, monitoring the development of professional knowledge, and organizing students' activities towards achieving specific goals. Students are encouraged to use textbooks, educational aids, lecture texts, handouts, electronic materials, virtual exhibitions, and displays effectively.

References:

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